
A PRACTICAL GUIDE TO INTERPRETABILITY METRICS FOR CHAIN OF THOUGHT REASONING

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ABSTRACT

Chain-of-Thought (CoT) reasoning is widely treated as evidence of interpretability in large language models. Yet, the presence of a plausible reasoning trace does not guarantee that the explanation is faithful, useful, or robust. This requires metrics that go beyond task accuracy, however available metrics are poorly aligned with the real-world constraints that practitioners face. This survey provides a practical guide to interpretability metrics for CoT reasoning, organizing them along three axes: the desiderata targeted by the metric, the evaluator type used to compute it, and the level of model access required. We catalog metrics from the literature and identify structural gaps in current evaluation practice. Our key finding is most faithfulness metrics that provide a causally-grounded evaluation require full model weight access, leaving practitioners evaluating proprietary models with correlation-based metrics. Other limitations include the requirement for ground-truth benchmarks, the common claim that metrics measure faithfulness when in practice they measure plausibility, and the lack of metrics for continuity, consistency and efficiency. The three-axis framework and accompanying tables are designed to support practitioners in selecting appropriate metrics given their application context and constraints, and to guide the research community towards the gaps that most urgently need addressing.

Keywords XAI · explainability · interpretability · metrics · CoT · LLMs · reasoning

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) are increasingly deployed in settings where their outputs directly inform human decisions. In clinical diagnosis, financial analysis, policy forecasting, and scientific inquiry, practitioners do not simply act on a model’s answer, but they also examine its reasoning. Chain-of-Thought (CoT) reasoning, in which a model verbalizes its thinking through a sequence of intermediate steps before or alongside a final answer, has become the dominant mode of explanation for these systems. Indeed, it is frequently treated as evidence of a model’s transparency, and approximately one quarter of CoT papers regard it as a sufficient condition for interpretability [1]. It is not.

A reasoning trace is explainable by construction, as it produces a human-readable account of the model’s response. But explainability is not interpretability. A CoT explanation is interpretable only if it faithfully reflects the internal process by which the model reached its conclusion, is useful and legible to the humans relying on it, and behaves robustly across the conditions in which it is deployed. The presence of a reasoning trace does not guarantee these properties. Models produce fluent, coherent explanations that justify answers driven by spurious biases without the bias appearing anywhere in the explanation [2, 3]. Corrupting intermediate reasoning steps has surprisingly little effect on final answer accuracy for many tasks [4]. These both demonstrate the presence of a CoT reasoning trace is neither necessary nor sufficient for a trustworthy or interpretable explanation [1, 5].

Measuring the interpretability of CoT reasoning requires evaluation metrics that go beyond task accuracy and surface plausibility. Yet the landscape of available metrics is fragmented, inconsistently applied, and poorly understood in terms of what each metric actually establishes [6, 7]. Metrics are routinely described as measuring faithfulness when

they measure plausibility [8, 9]. Evaluations are predominantly designed for verifiable tasks such as Mathematics, but these cannot be transferred to more open-ended settings with multiple valid answers [10, 7]. Human evaluation is rarely conducted, and when it is, samples are too small to support statistical conclusions [11, 12]. Furthermore, the metrics that provide the strongest evidence of faithfulness require either open-weight model access or repeated inference, making them largely inaccessible to closed-source models where interpretable CoT is most needed [13].

This survey provides a practical guide to CoT interpretability metrics for practitioners and researchers who need to evaluate reasoning traces under real-world constraints. We identify and catalog all metrics in the literature applicable to CoT reasoning and organize them along three axes that reflect the decisions a practitioner actually faces: what interpretability properties are relevant to their application, what evaluators are feasible given their data and resources, and what level of model access is available. This three-axes framework enables practitioners to identify which metrics apply to their specific setting, understand what each metric can and cannot establish, and compose metric bundles that provide stronger collective evidence than any single measure alone. The motivations for this work, its contribution relative to existing surveys, and the paper structure, are described in the subsections below.

1.1 Motivations

In the field of LLMs, particularly in the context of CoT [14], most studies primarily evaluate LLM’s response accuracy and the plausibility of generated reasoning traces (the latter often confused with an explanation). In many human-in-the-loop settings, the interpretability of a reasoning trace is far more important than accuracy, as it enables human’s to understand how the model actually reached its final answer. For instance, it can uncover how specific features affect the final answer, potentially unveiling a mechanistic understanding of a problem or model biases [15]. Despite evidence showing the presence of a CoT reasoning trace is neither necessary nor sufficient for interpretability, it is still treated as an interpretability technique [1]. There is an urgent need for rigorous interpretability metrics to verify how CoT reasoning traces link to actual model behavior, i.e., explainability [1, 5, 16].

The proliferation of LLMs in critical domains such as healthcare [17], finance [18], and government policy [19] renders interpretability of the CoT even more urgent, as humans focus on CoT reasoning traces to guide their decisions, for instance, on medical diagnoses [20, 21], or to refine questions in interactive Machine Learning (ML) scenarios [22, 23]. We argue that meaningful interpretability metrics for CoT reasoning not only enable better evaluation of LLMs but also provide potential insights that could be used during training to shape and improve model behavior.

1.2 Comparison to other surveys

To our best knowledge, there are currently no surveys focusing exclusively on interpretability metrics for evaluating CoT reasoning traces. Reviews predating the emergence of CoT reasoning in LLMs provide valuable taxonomic foundations for explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) in the field, but do not address the specific challenges of evaluating whether generative reasoning traces are linked to actual internal model behavior [24, 25, 26, 27]. Existing XAI surveys primarily focus on post-hoc interpretability methods like feature attribution, saliency maps, and concept-based explanations, treating natural language explanations (NLEs) as one category among many rather than the primary object of evaluation [28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 6].

Within the space of NLEs, we further restrict our scope to *Chain-of-Thought* (CoT) reasoning: a reasoning trace generated directly by an LLM as part of its response to an input, prior to or alongside a final answer. This distinguishes CoT from post-hoc NLEs, which are generated after a prediction has been made, and from NLEs produced by a separate model to explain another model’s output. We include CoT generated in response to both classification-style inputs, where a specific prediction is expected, and open-ended inputs where multiple valid responses exist. Multimodal inputs are within scope, but we consider only text-format reasoning outputs.

Some surveys narrow further to specific techniques, such as mechanistic interpretability [33, 34], which captures one evaluator type in our framework but does not contribute a systematic review of the overall landscape. Similarly, some surveys focus on a subset of the desiderata presented in this paper, for example, looking at metrics for safety [32] or hallucination detection [35].

Surveys that evaluate CoT reasoning mainly focus on comparing different prompting techniques to achieve better accuracy or performance [36, 37]. Where interpretability (i.e., whether the reasoning traces correspond to what the model actually used to reach a certain output) is taken into account, evaluation is typically limited to verifiable tasks like math, science, logic, and factual reasoning [10, 7]. These settings are often unsuitable proxies for more complex reasoning in free-text contexts [7], and the trade-off between optimizing for interpretability metrics and maintaining task performance remains an open question [38].

Figure 1: Illustration of paper structure.

There is a growing recognition that XAI evaluation requires user studies, yet existing surveys either focus entirely on functionally grounded metrics that do not involve users [6], or entirely on human-based evaluation [11, 39, 20, 40]. Finally, some surveys focus on what developments in XAI are required for real-world deployment rather than systematically reviewing what evaluation methods currently exist [41, 42, 43].

Our work builds on the taxonomy and metric categorization of eValuation of XAI (VXAI) [6] by extending it to include human-grounded evaluations and properties specific to CoT reasoning. We highlight the practicalities of metric selection for practitioners to further the goals of usable XAI [44], and ensure that interpretability metrics are not only applicable to verifiable domains [7]. This survey addresses the gap for an exclusive CoT reasoning focus with a systematic treatment of what each interpretability metric actually measures, for which desiderata, and under what constraints.

1.3 Paper Structure

This survey is structured around five research questions:

- RQ1:** What are the desired interpretability properties of CoT reasoning traces that can lead to a meaningful explanation of model behavior?
- RQ2:** What evaluator types are used to assess these properties, and what evidence or ground truth does each require?
- RQ3:** What level of model access does each evaluator type require, and what does this imply for which models can be evaluated?
- RQ4:** What metrics currently exist, and how do they relate to desired properties, evaluator types and model access constraints?
- RQ5:** What are the limitations of existing metrics, and what open problems does this create for practitioners and the research community?

Figure 1 displays the content of each section. Section 2 establishes the key distinctions between interpretability and explainability, introduces CoT reasoning and its relationship to other natural language explanation (NLE) types, and motivates the need for evaluation paradigms that go beyond task performance. Section 3 introduces the three-axis framework that organizes the survey. Sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 define each axis in turn. Section 4 catalogs all identified metrics organized by metric family. Section 5 analyses the coverage gaps, limitations, and open problems revealed by the catalog, while Section 6 outlines directions for future work.

1.4 Review Methodology

We now introduce the methodology with which we scrutinized the surveys discussed in section 1.2. Due to the large number of papers in this field, we focused on first identifying relevant existing survey papers and then followed citations

Source	Category	Sub-Category	Papers Identified	Included
arXiv	Survey		32	18
Scopus	Survey		25	5
Identified from citations of query results	Additional Surveys		16	8
	General		26	13
	XAI Metrics	Explanans-Centric	94	39
		Model Observation	13	6
		Input Intervention	28	12
		Model Intervention	17	5
Identified from all included paper citations	Survey		4	2
	Non-survey		2	2
Additions from manual search	General			3
Total			197	113

Table 1: Summary of paper identification and screening process. Citations from relevant sections was conducted from survey papers identified in the initial database and other source searches. Additional surveys identified through this process were also screened and relevant citations were added.

therein to reach papers introducing relevant interpretability metrics. The numbers of identified and chosen papers, and their respective categories, can be found in Table 1. For the surveys, we queried Scopus for peer-reviewed papers and arXiv for pre-prints using the queries in Appendix 8.1. We searched for survey papers that explicitly mentioned XAI for LLMs, reasoning, or CoT, or surveys looking at the evaluation of XAI. To be included in this review, surveys were required to contain a dedicated section discussing metrics for interpretability. We only include surveys focusing on multimodal tasks if they evaluate on text generated during CoT reasoning directly. Following paper screening, 23 surveys met the inclusion criteria and were retained in this review. From here, citations identified in relevant survey sections were screened, and the corresponding papers were included as metrics if they met the following criteria:

1. Metric measured a property of interpretability, not simply accuracy;
2. The paper was the primary source of a metric;
3. The metric was designed for Natural Language Explanations (NLEs) and could be applied to CoT reasoning without any changes;

To assess reliability of the screening process, five authors independently rated 25 boundary-case papers for inclusion. Initial inter-rater agreement yielded a Fleiss’ Kappa value $\kappa = 0.55 \pm 0.06$ [45]. Disagreements clustered around two boundary cases: metrics designed for text summarization or recommendation systems, which were excluded on the grounds that summarization quality is not equivalent to reasoning faithfulness even when CoT traces contain summary-like steps; and evaluation primitives such as BERTScore and BLEU, which were included under criterion 3 as evaluator components used as part of Similarity metrics, rather than standalone interpretability metrics. Following discussion and clarification of these boundaries decisions were revised, yielding $\kappa = 0.71 \pm 0.06$.

2 Background

A foundational distinction in this survey is between *interpretability* and *explainability*, two terms used inconsistently across the literature. We refer to interpretability as the understanding of *what* the model deemed important and *how* the model produces a specific output, while explainability addresses the question of *why* the model produced an output grounded on the *what* and *how* (when available) [46]. CoT reasoning, by construction, produces a human-readable account of the model’s response, but does not necessarily use the *what* and *how* (i.e., the interpretability component), since the textual trace need not faithfully reflect the internal computational process that produced it. Hallucinations in reasoning chains and the susceptibility of explanations to adversarial manipulation are both symptoms of this gap. This survey is therefore concerned not with whether CoT reasoning is correct, but with the degree to which it fulfills interpretability properties appropriate to its application: whether the reasoning is faithful to the model’s internal process, legible and useful to the humans relying on it, and robust across the conditions in which it is deployed.

We restrict our scope to black-box models that are not inherently interpretable. This explicitly includes transformer-based LLMs despite the availability of their self-attention weights. Although attention has been proposed as a form

of explanation, raw attention weights do not consistently align with gradient-based feature attributions or other explainability methods and therefore cannot be assumed to faithfully reflect model decision-making [8, 47].

2.1 Natural Language Explanations and Chain-of-Thought Reasoning

Explanations produced by Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems take many forms. The VXAI framework[6] identifies five principal explanation types: feature attributions, which assign relevance scores to input features; concept explanations, which identify higher-level human-interpretable abstractions in model representations; example-based explanations, which characterize model behavior through representative or counterfactual instances; white-box surrogates, which approximate a black-box model with an inherently interpretable one; and Natural Language Explanations (NLEs), which are textual justifications generated in response to a model’s input or output [6]. This survey focuses exclusively on NLEs, specifically CoT reasoning traces.

Chain-of-Thought prompting was introduced as a technique for eliciting step-by-step reasoning from language models. It has been shown to substantially improve model accuracy on complex tasks [14], but it can also lead to more hallucinations [48]. The faithfulness of CoT reasoning has also been shown to vary substantially across tasks and model scales [4], meaning the plausibility of the trace cannot be taken as evidence of its faithfulness.

However, CoT reasoning encompasses several distinct output types that differ substantially in their relationship to the model’s internal computation, and this distinction has direct consequences for which interpretability metrics are applicable. The most common form in practice is the externalized reasoning trace, in which a model verbalizes intermediate steps prior to a final answer, typically delimited by special tokens such as <think> and <\think>. However, this visible trace may not correspond to the computation that produced the answer. In reasoning models such as DeepSeek-R1 [49] and OpenAI o1 [50], the visible trace may be a summarized or post-processed version of an internal scratchpad that is never directly exposed to users. For such models, metrics applied to the visible reasoning may be evaluating a summary rather than the computation itself.

The relationship between verbalized reasoning and faithfulness is further complicated by evidence that models produce systematically different reasoning when they believe their trace is observable. It has been shown reasoning models do not verbalize the reasoning that drove their conclusions [5], and will produce coherent traces to justify an answer without acknowledging the features that actually determined it [2]. Corrupting intermediate reasoning steps - through early answering, insertion of errors, or addition of filler tokens - also has surprisingly little effect on final answer accuracy for many tasks [4]. A recent framework formalized this distinction by separating CoT-as-rationalization, in which the model explains a decision already reached, from CoT-as-computation, in which the trace is a necessary component of the inference itself [51].

The type of CoT a model produces is determined by its architecture, training objective and inference configuration, all factors that are fixed by the time an evaluator applies a metric. This survey therefore does not restrict its scope to any single CoT type. Instead, we treat the computational role of the trace as a dimension of uncertainty that modulates how metrics should be interpreted. CoT-as-rationalization traces warrant additional caution, as the visible output may be a summary of an internal scratchpad or a post-reasoning justification of the final answer rather than the computation itself.

2.2 Evaluation Paradigms and the Human-in-the-Loop Setting

The foundational taxonomy for evaluating interpretability methods distinguishes three levels grounded in who performs the assessment and under what conditions [52]. *Application-grounded* evaluation involves real users performing real tasks; it is the most representative of genuine deployment conditions but the most resource-intensive. *Human-grounded* evaluation uses non-expert participants on simplified tasks, trading grounding in real-world use cases with scalability. *Functionally-grounded* evaluation replaces human participants with automated proxies entirely, enabling large-scale assessment at the cost of assumptions about what those proxies measure. Because explanations are ultimately meant to aid humans, human-grounded evaluation retains a privileged status as the closest available approximation of real-world utility [52, 6].

More recent frameworks have recast this distinction through the lens of purpose. The BLUE/RED XAI distinction separates evaluations oriented towards end-user value, assessing whether explanations are useful and meaningful to the people relying on them, from those oriented towards model validation, assessing whether explanations are technically correct and faithful to model behavior [53]. This distinction is particularly consequential in human-in-the-loop settings, where a practitioner or domain expert uses a model’s CoT reasoning to inform a decision. For example, in clinical diagnosis, financial analysis, or scientific inquiry, the relevant question is not only whether the explanation is technically faithful to the model’s computation, but whether it is understandable and useful for the user’s task and expertise.

To organize the desiderata that follow from these dual requirements, the Co-12 framework provides a structured decomposition of explanation quality into twelve properties spanning Content, Presentation, and User dimensions [26]. Building on this, the VXAI framework derives a refined set of seven desiderata suited to functionality-grounded evaluation: Parsimony, Plausibility, Coverage, Fidelity, Continuity, Consistency and Efficiency [6]. These converge on a common foundation: explanations should be faithful to the model’s true reasoning process (Fidelity) whilst remaining concise enough to support human understanding (Parsimony), and should behave reliably across similar inputs and repeated evaluations (Continuity and Consistency).

Despite the recognized importance of human-centered evaluation, fewer than one in five XAI papers include any form of user study [11]. This reflects genuine practical constraints: recruiting domain experts is costly and slow [52], sample sizes tend to be small and limit statistical power [12], and human judgments are susceptible to systematic distortions including confirmation bias and social desirability effects [54, 6, 55]. Furthermore, any explanation, including meaningless placebo explanations, has been shown to increase perceived trust relative to no explanation at all [56], which calls into question the validity of trust or plausibility ratings as standalone proxies for explanation quality. Research in social science further complicates the picture: people prefer contrastive explanations that address why *this* outcome rather than some alternative, and respond to the most selective and proximate cause rather than the most complete one [54, 57]. The result is that automated, functionally-grounded metrics dominate the literature even for properties that are fundamentally human-centered in nature.

Understanding precisely what these automated metrics measure, what they cannot measure, and which desiderata currently lack adequate coverage is the central problem this survey addresses. The framework introduced in Section 3 provides a structured approach to navigating this landscape.

3 A Framework for CoT Interpretability Evaluation

A practitioner evaluating the interpretability of a system faces three dimensions which require decisions to narrow the space of applicable interpretability metrics: what properties of the reasoning trace matter for this application, what computational resources and data are available to measure them, and what level of access to the underlying model is feasible. These three decisions correspond to the three axes along which this survey organizes the existing metric landscape: Section 3.1 covers *desiderata*, Section 3.2 *evaluators*, and Section 3.3 *model access*.

Identifying which interpretability properties are relevant to their application relates directly to the deployment context, and it is unlikely that a single metric will capture every desired property. Table 2 defines the full set of desiderata identified in this survey, synthesizing from the Co-12 framework [26] and the VXAI framework [6] with additional properties specific to the CoT context: *Factuality* and *Utility*. These are not captured by existing frameworks, which were derived primarily from functionally-grounded evaluation, but emerge consistently as critical in the literature on CoT reasoning in high-stakes human-in-the-loop deployments [20, 12].

Another consideration is how interpretability can be measured given available data and resources. This survey identifies six evaluator types, ordered by increasing correlation with human judgment and increasing computational or human cost. Like desiderata, many metrics combine multiple evaluator types or allow options. For example, it is common practice to compare either Human or LLM judges to a few different similarity scores. Section 3.2 describes each evaluator type in detail, including the evidence or ground truth each requires and its known limitations for CoT evaluation.

The final constraint is the level of access the evaluator requires to the model being studied, which determines whether a metric can be applied to closed-source models or is limited to models with freely available weights. Following the VXAI framework [6], this survey organizes metrics into five families of progressively deeper model dependency. Section 3.3 defines each family and discusses the practical implications of each access level for CoT evaluation.

All interpretability metrics identified in this survey are cataloged in Section 4. Figure 2 illustrates their distribution across the three axes of desiderata, evaluators, and model access, revealing several structural patterns discussed below. In the left hand plot, Fidelity and Plausibility account for the large majority of metrics on the desiderata axis, reflecting both the centrality of these properties to CoT evaluation and the relative neglect of properties such as Parsimony and Efficiency. On the right-hand evaluators plot, Predictive Performance and Overlap-based Similarity dominate, whilst Mechanistic Interpretability, LLM Judge and Human Judge evaluators are comparatively rare, reflecting the practical barriers to their use rather than their theoretical value. The low concentration of metrics in the Model Intervention family on the *y*-axis show preferences towards metrics that don’t require full model access, likely so that large proprietary LLMs can be evaluated as these are frequently the highest performing for downstream tasks.

Figure 2: Heatmap showing the number of metrics for each Metric Family and which Desiderata (left) and Evaluators (right) they correspond to.

3.1 Desiderata

Evaluating the interpretability of CoT reasoning requires first establishing what properties a high-quality explanation should possess. These desiderata are the target of any evaluation metrics, and a metric is only meaningful if the property it measures is one we actually care about. Several frameworks have proposed taxonomies of explanation quality properties, and whilst most cover a wide scope of all explanation types, they can be directly applied to CoT reasoning.

The Co-12 framework decomposes explanation quality into twelve properties spanning Content dimensions (Correctness, Completeness, Consistency, Continuity, Contrastivity, Covariate Complexity), Presentation dimensions (Compactness, Composition, Confidence) and User dimensions (Context, Coherence, Controllability) [26]. The VXAI framework, derived from a systematic review of 362 evaluation metrics, refines these into seven desiderata suited to functionality-grounded evaluation: Parsimony, Plausibility, Coverage, Fidelity, Continuity, Consistency and Efficiency [6]. We adopt the VXAI properties, and for an analysis of the overlap between Co-12 and VXAI we direct readers to [12].

Table 2 synthesizes desiderata used in this survey and their definitions, mapping them to any equivalents, where appropriate, and indicating which require human-centered evaluation. We adopt the seven VXAI properties and propose two additions, Factuality and Utility, which are critical for CoT reasoning in human-in-the-loop settings and described in more detail below.

Several properties cited as desiderata in broader XAI literature are not included in this survey. Composition, Controllability and Confidence are based more on the system design and outputs than direct properties of CoT reasoning [26]. Fairness and Safety are similarly excluded because they are model-level properties only partially reflected in explanations, for example safety is defined as model’s capacity to prevent harm [58]. Satisfaction can be better understood as a consequence of other properties being met than as an independently measurable target [61]. Trustworthiness, whilst widely referenced [18, 43], lacks a consistent definition across the literature and is more practically characterized through a combination of Fidelity, Consistency and Plausibility than a property that can be directly measured.

3.1.1 Factuality

Factuality, sometimes called Groundedness, is a critical concern for LLMs which are prone to hallucinations [62]. Interpretability measures often refer to factual consistency. For example, for in-context learning (ICL), explanations can be considered faithful if they only contain information inferable or stated by provided documents [63]. Measuring the factual consistency of generated text is a popular approach to understand and reduce hallucinations [64, 65], and factual explanations have been shown to correlate better with human judgment [66]. The ability to ground responses in verifiable information can be essential for reliability in sectors such as finance [18], making this desiderata critical for certain tasks.

Desiderata	Human-Centred	Definitions
Parsimony[6]	✗	Explanation method should keep the explanation concise to support interpretability.[6]
Plausibility [6]	✓	the extent that an explanation resonates with and is deemed acceptable by a human audience [36] Explanation method should shape explanations to align with human expectations [6] How convincing the interpretation is to humans [8]
Coverage [6]	✗	Explanation method should provide an explanation for every input that requires explaining [6]
Fidelity [6] (Faithfulness)	✗	Explanation method should ensure the explanations reflect the model’s true reasoning [6]
	✗	An explanation that accurately represents the reasoning process behind the model’s prediction, measured as the extent as likelihood of being faithful [8]
	✗	Accurately describes the models decision-making process [9]
Continuity [6][26]	✗	Similar inputs should yield similar explanations [6]
Stability Robustness	✗	Resilience to adversarial attacks and distribution shifts [58]
	✗	How resilient or consistent a given explanation is under various circumstances [36]
Consistency [6][26]	✗	Explanation method should produce stable explanations across repeated evaluations [6]
Efficiency [6]	✗	Explanation method should compute explanations efficiently and broadly [6]
Factuality (Groundedness)	✗	A models ability to ground responses in verifiable information [58] [7]
Utility [59]	✓	how well humans or LLM judges can predict a model’s outputs based on its explanations [60]
	✓	the degree to which users feel they can sufficiently understand the AI system being explained [61]
	✓	maximizing information conveyed to the audience [36]

Table 2: Key desiderata for natural language explanation methods.

3.1.2 Utility

Utility (or Usefulness) represents the in-context experience by the user, acknowledging that an explanation can be technically correct but still useless for a specific task [59]. We identify three operationalizations of Utility in the literature: Simulatability, the extent to which an observer can accurately predict a model’s outputs given its explanation [60]; Understandability, the degree to which users feel they can sufficiently comprehend how the system functions [61, 11]; and Informativeness, the amount of task-relevant information the explanation conveys to its intended audience [36] - for example whether a reasoning step aids derivation of the answer [67], or supports human decision-making [18].

These operationalizations are grounded in cognitive psychology, where mental models - representations of how a person understands a system given their task, goals, and situation - provide the theoretical basis for measuring user comprehension of AI [61, 54]. Traditionally elicited directly from human participants, mental models are increasingly approximated using LLM-as-a-judge as a scalable proxy for Simulatability [60].

3.2 Evaluators

A CoT interpretability metric is only as meaningful as the evaluator used to compute it. The choice of evaluator is constrained by what evidence is available against which the explanation can be assessed. Some evaluators require a reference explanation or ground-truth label, in the form of a human-written rationale, a benchmark answer, or a trusted external knowledge source. Others operate without any reference, relying on comparing explanations themselves or using signals from the generative model producing the explanations.

Reference explanations are typically found from natural language explanation benchmarks such as e-SNLI [68], CoS-E [69], TruthfulQA [70], and multimodal benchmarks VQA-X and ACT-X [71] for full free-text rationales. Alternatively, some datasets provide partial evidence such as highlighted spans, supporting facts, or structured decompositions, including ERASER [72], ROSCOE [73] and e-CARE [74]. However, reference explanations are expensive to collect and rarely sufficient, as several different reasoning traces may be able to justify the same answer equally well. As a result, low similarity to a reference explanation does not necessarily imply low interpretability or a poor quality explanation.

Within verifiable domains such as mathematics, recent advancements use formal proof languages to enable automated verification of proof correctness without any reference explanation [75, 76]. However formal verifiability is only valid

for specific tasks, not CoT reasoning in general, and therefore evaluation methods that depend on it cannot transfer to unverifiable settings.

We identify six evaluator types, presented in order of increasing correlation with human judgment but also increasing computational or human cost. Evaluators earlier in this ordering are more accessible and widely used but more abstracted from what interpretability actually requires, those later are more directly meaningful but harder to apply. In practice, many metric implementations are composed of multiple evaluator types. Meta-evaluations that assess the evaluators themselves, primarily through correlation with human judgment, are discussed in Section 5.

3.2.1 Predictive Performance

The most widely used evaluator is predictive performance on a downstream task, typically computed using classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1, or AUCROC. When applied to a static model output, task performance is mostly limited to measuring Plausibility, confirming that the explanation is consistent with a correct answer, but says little about if it reflects the model’s true reasoning process. However when embedded within a designed intervention, a resulting change in task performance can serve as evidence of Fidelity. For example, a drop in accuracy when a reasoning trace is corrupted suggests the model was genuinely using that reasoning, or a change in performance when a spurious feature is inserted can measure Fidelity and Continuity [2, 4].

The use of open-source benchmarks has the limitation of data contamination, where more recent language models have seen the benchmark in pretraining data, meaning performance scores may reflect memorization rather than reasoning [77]. This is particularly consequential for CoT evaluation, where, given knowledge of the correct answer, models are able to produce plausible reasoning and score highly on task performance metrics [4].

3.2.2 Overlap-based Similarity

Overlap-based similarity metrics compare a generated CoT reasoning to a reference explanation or to another trace from the same model. The most widely used are lexical overlap measures including exact match, n-gram F1, BLEU [78], ROUGE [79] and METEOR [80]. These were originally developed for machine translation and summarization and are easy to compute, but are often too brittle for reasoning because valid explanations can differ substantially in wording and structure [81]. When used for interpretability evaluation they are shown to have low correlation with human judgment [25, 35].

These challenges compound for CoT reasoning, where there may be many valid explanations for the same answer or intermediate steps may be partially correct, making comparison to gold-standard rationale based on final-answers a particularly weak signal of explanation quality in this context [82].

3.2.3 Model-based Similarity

Model-based similarity metrics address the brittleness of lexical overlap by comparing semantic representations of texts rather than their surface form. BERTScore [83], BARTScore [84] and MoverScore [85] are the most widely applied, computing similarity between contextualized token embeddings of generated and reference texts. These tend to correlate better with human judgment than overlap-based metrics [86], but still do not account for the possibility of multiple valid but semantically distinct explanations.

A distinct class of model-based evaluator applies Natural Language Inference (NLI) models to assess whether an explanation is supported by or entails a given input, context or reference. Rather than measuring surface similarity, entailment-based metrics assess logical support, making them more appropriate for evaluating Factuality [7]. Prior work in summarization evaluation suggests entailment-based metrics correlate more strongly with human judgments of faithfulness than similarity scores [25, 81, 87]. For CoT, entailment can be applied between the explanation and source context, between adjacent reasoning steps or between the full trace and the final answer. Their main limitation is they struggle to interpret nuanced text which considers both supporting and contradicting arguments [7], and sometimes the scores prioritize sentences with the same subject matter even if they do not convey the same information [35].

Models fine-tuned specifically for explanation comparison also fall within this category. The COMET model family provides evaluation models for machine translation that can be adapted to explanation comparison [88], whilst BLEURT [89] and SESCORE [90] achieve comparable performance trained on synthetic errors, without requiring human annotation.

3.2.4 Intrinsic Interpretability

Intrinsic evaluators use information already available from the generative model itself, without requiring any external reference or ground truth. These include uncertainty measures derived from token probability distributions, entropy-based scores and V-information, a measure of the information the reasoning trace provides beyond what is already contained in the input [7]. A significant advantage is that these metrics do not require any external reference data and only require inference access to the model, making them applicable in a wide range of settings.

Their limitation is that they are indirect indicators of interpretability; token probabilities may reflect model calibration and distributional properties rather than quality or faithfulness of an explanation. Attention-weights, sometimes proposed as an intrinsic explanation signal, have been shown not to consistently align with other explainability methods like feature attribution [91, 92], and should not be assumed to reflect the model’s reasoning.

3.2.5 Mechanistic Interpretability

Mechanistic interpretability provides a framework for evaluating the interpretability of CoT reasoning by reverse-engineering the model’s internal computations into human-understandable algorithms [13]. These methods require access to the model internals and typically involve probing, activation patching, ablation, causal attribution, circuit analysis or sparse autoencoder decomposition. Their goal is to test whether an explanation is faithful to the specific computational process implemented by the model [93, 13].

However mechanistic interpretability evaluation faces significant technical and conceptual challenges in the LLM setting. Probing identifies correlations between activations and features but does not prove that the model uses that information to make a decision, only intervention-based methods like patching or ablation provide causal evidence of functional necessity [93]. Large models often possess redundant backup circuits, so if one path is ablated another may compensate, making it difficult to define a single true mechanism for a reasoning step [94]. Research on Llama-2 suggests LLMs often use multiple parallel pathways for answer generation using CoT, collecting information simultaneously from question context, prompt and generated CoT, meaning a single true mechanism is hard to identify [94]. Mechanistic interpretability evaluators also require full access to model weights and internals, restricting their applicability to open-source models and making them inaccessible for the large proprietary LLMs where interpretable CoT is most needed.

3.2.6 Human and LLM Judges

Human evaluation remains the most direct and preferred way to assess properties that are inherently human-centered, such as Plausibility and Utility, and is especially important when no reference explanation exists. It is typically conducted through interview or Likert-scale survey [95], and remains the evaluator most closely aligned with the real-world purpose of CoT explanations.

Conducting human evaluation rigorously requires attention to annotator population, protocol design, and statistical power. Domain experts are better positioned to assess Factuality and Utility in high-stakes settings but are costly to recruit and can exhibit confirmation bias [54]. Crowd-sourced annotators are more scalable but tend to conflate Plausibility with correctness, rating fluent and confident explanations highly regardless of their interpretability [8]. Annotation protocol design affects what is actually being measured; for example, Utility can be measured through forward simulation, where participants predict model outputs given an explanation [52], or through mental model elicitation, where participants articulate their understanding of how the system functions [61]. Human ratings using Likert-scales in these settings have shown to be inconsistent without anchoring examples [12]. Finally, human evaluations in the XAI literature frequently use samples too small to support statistical conclusions [12, 11].

LLM-as-a-judge methods have emerged as a scalable alternative, with recent work suggesting that prompted or fine-tuned LLMs often correlate well with human judgment [96]. For CoT reasoning, they are particularly useful because they can evaluate long and semantically diverse traces better than lexical metrics. Nevertheless they still have limitations such as sensitivity to prompt wording, position bias and robustness to adversarial attacks [97, 35, 98]. A further concern specific to interpretability evaluation is that LLMs perform poorly on causal reasoning tasks [48], meaning LLM judges are likely unreliable evaluators for metrics assessing causal relationships. Where compute is not limited, it has been shown that inference-time-scaling improves the accuracy and fairness of judge LLMs [98, 5]. However, whether LLM judges can serve as a reliable proxy for human judgment, and under what conditions, remains an open question that is discussed in Section 5.

3.3 Model Access

After identifying target desiderata and feasible evaluator type, the final constraint on metric selection is the level of access the evaluator requires to the model being studied. This determines whether a metric can be applied to closed-source models accessible only via API, or whether it is restricted to models with freely available weights and internals.

The VXAI framework organizes metrics along this dimension using the concept of contextuality, the degree to which a metric depends on or intervenes in the underlying model or data [6]. We adopt this organization with one modification; in VXAI, metrics requiring a ground-truth dataset are placed in the A Priori Constrained family on the basis that they depend on specific data conditions established in advance. However for CoT reasoning the available formats of reference evidence are far broader than for other explanation types; from full rationales and partial evidence to formally verifiable rules to agreement with mechanistic interpretability findings. The presence of ground-truth data is therefore more relevant to the evaluator, and what reference data it requires to be computed, rather than a constraint on the model access.

We instead place metrics requiring ground-truth data into families based on the level of model access rather than all within A Priori Constrained. Metrics based on a comparison to ground-truth rationales are placed within the Explanans-Centric family since their only model access requirement is the explanation text itself. Metrics that are based on agreement with mechanistic interpretability results are placed into Model Intervention as calculating the reference activations requires access to and altering of the model weights directly.

With this modification, we categorize model access using the five metric families defined in the VXAI framework [6], ordered by increasing depth of interaction with the model:

1. Explanans-Centric: The metric operate on the explanation text and its corresponding input alone, with no dependency on the underlying model.
2. Model Observation: The metric requires querying the model to obtain outputs, token probabilities or internal activations, but does not modify the model or its inputs in any way.
3. Input Intervention: The metric requires creating or perturbing input data and observing the resulting change in predictions or explanations, requiring repeated model inference but not access to model weights.
4. Model Intervention: The metric requires altering the model itself through retraining, parameter randomization or weight editing, requiring full access to model internals.
5. A Priori Constrained: Requires specific architectural choices, training setups or experimental conditions to be established before evaluation.

A practitioner evaluating CoT reasoning within an existing system, where metrics cannot rely on re-prompting, is restricted to the Explanans-Centric and Model Observation families. Access to a proprietary model via API opens up Input Intervention, but is potentially still constrained by inference costs and token limits. The final two families are inaccessible for large proprietary LLMs as Model Intervention requires access to model weights, and A Priori Constrained requires experimental control from the outset. This is a problem for CoT reasoning evaluation, where proprietary LLMs are the most widely deployed, and in practice we identified no metrics in the A Priori Constrained family as it is not inherently useful to identify CoT reasoning constrained to a single dataset and architecture.

4 Metric Catalog

This section catalogs all metrics identified in this survey, organized by metric family following the taxonomy defined in Section 3.3. Within each family, metrics are grouped by functional similarity, shared desiderata and evaluator type, as many metrics in the literature represent minor variations on a common methodology. Full details of each metric, including desiderata coverage and evaluator composition, are provided in the appendix; Table 3 maps metrics to desiderata and Table 4 maps metrics to evaluator types. Figure 2 provides a visual overview of the distribution of metrics across all three axes. A key observation running through this catalog is the asymmetry between desiderata coverage, with the majority of metrics covering Fidelity and Plausibility whilst other properties having comparatively low coverage, particularly at lower model access levels where most practitioners operate.

4.1 Explanans-Centric

Explanans-Centric metrics operate on the explanation text and its corresponding input alone, requiring no access to the underlying model. They represent the most accessible family for practitioners, applicable to closer-sources models and

model-monitoring systems with the least computational overhead. As Figure 2 shows, this family has strong coverage of Plausibility and Factuality, but no coverage of Continuity or Consistency, which by definition require repeated inference or input perturbation.

4.1.1 Explanation Size

The simplest metric in the entire catalog is explanation size, which directly measures Parsimony [6]. For CoT reasoning, the size of the explanation could be measured by number of sentences, words, tokens or characters. Whilst trivially computable, measuring Parsimony alone is not generally useful, a concise explanation may omit critical reasoning steps, whilst a lengthy one may be thorough rather than redundant.

4.1.2 Ground Truth Comparison

The largest group of Explanans-Centric metrics compares generated explanations against reference rationales from benchmark datasets. The choice of similarity measure within this group determines both what is measured and how well that measurement is likely to correlate with human judgment, as discussed in Section 3.2. Overlap-based measures, predominantly BLEU [78] and ROUGE [79], remain the most widely used despite their known brittleness for reasoning evaluation [81], with adoption across a large number of NLE benchmarks and evaluation frameworks [99, 100, 71, 69, 101, 102, 103, 104, 105, 106, 72, 107, 108, 109]. Model-based similarity measures such as BERTScore [83], and NLI or fine-tuned evaluation models COMET [88], BLUERT [89], BARTScore [84], SESCORE [90] and UniEval [110] correlate better with human judgment and are increasingly preferred. LLM-as-a-judge has more recently been applied to score explanations against the same criteria used by original human annotators, as in TruthfulQA [70] and WHOOPS [111], offering a scalable alternative to fixed similarity metrics whilst introducing its own biases discussed in Section 3.2. A fundamental limitation of all ground-truth comparison metrics is that reference explanations are expensive to collect and are rarely exhaustive. In CoT reasoning it is highly likely that multiple distinct reasoning traces may justify the same answer equally well, meaning that low similarity to a single reference does not imply low explanation quality. This problem is particularly severe for open-ended or unverifiable tasks, the settings where interpretability evaluation is most needed.

4.1.3 Factual Comparison

Factual Comparison metrics assess the degree to which an explanation’s claims are grounded in verifiable information. Factuality is often approximated based on overlap with a provided knowledge source using n-grams or tokens [66]. Another common method is entailment-based metrics that test if the explanation is logically supported by the input context, including Q² [112] and factENT [113]. A limitation of model-based similarity scores for Factuality is often semantically similar tokens do not convey the same fact, meaning that high similarity scores may just represent similar topics rather than factuality agreement [35]. *fact_{acc}* [114] uses a named-entity-recognition model to extract entities and a classifier to identify their relations, then calculates factual accuracy based on matching relations in input and explanation. FACTSCORE [65] and Principle Knowledge Collection [115] decompose explanations into atomic claims and verify each independently using an LLM judge, representing the most granular approach in this group. The Causal Explanation Quality (CEQ) score [74] additionally applies causal attribution to determine whether a fact is appropriately incorporated into the explanation rather than merely mentioned.

4.1.4 Input Contrastivity and Inter-Reasoning Metrics

Input Contrastivity metrics assess whether explanations are specific to their input rather than generic, meaning each unique input should result in a unique explanation [6]. ROSCOE introduces several metrics in this group, including Semantic Similarity and Source Consistency, which measure logical entailment between generated reasoning and source context [73]. Inter-reasoning metrics extend this by evaluating if internal structure of the reasoning chain itself is generic or specific to prior steps, rather than its relation to traces generated by alternative inputs. ROSCOE’s semantic alignment metrics assess how well information from the source or prior-steps is used in subsequent reasoning steps through model-based similarity methods [73]. Correctness and Information Gain [67] use point wise V-information to measure the contribution of each step towards the final answer, providing a measure of the Utility of information in CoT reasoning with respect to a final outcome.

4.1.5 Simulatability

Simulatability metrics assess whether an explanation conveys sufficient information about a model’s behavior for an observer to accurately predict how the model will respond to new inputs, directly measuring Utility. With a single desiderata, the metrics in this group vary with respect to which evaluators they select as the observer. Leakage-Adjusted

Simulatability [36] measures the improvement in a student model’s task performance when the explanation is added to its input. The `acc_improvement` metric [60] captures the additional predictive benefit of a model’s self-explanation over its raw output using an LLM judge. This tests whether an explanation enables accurate prediction of model outputs on diverse counterfactual inputs. Counterfactual Simulatability [116] measures both the diversity of counterfactuals the explanation covers and the fraction of cases where an observer’s inference matches the model’s output, with human inference approximated by entailment or LLM judge. Notably, human results in this setting have been shown to be accurately recreated using LLM-as-a-judge [116], suggesting Simulatability may be appropriate to evaluate without human studies. Human evaluation of Simulatability is conducted either through forward simulation studies, where users are asked to predict model outputs, or through mental model elicitation, where users articulate their understanding of how the system functions [61, 95]. Human Perception metrics [95] additionally assess Utility directly through interview and Likert-scale survey.

4.1.6 Input Coverage

Input coverage metrics assess whether explanations are generated for every input that requires one [6]. In the CoT context this is most relevant to refusal behavior. Hallucination and Safety refusal measure the percentage of appropriate refusals and the harmful content of explanations accompanying refusals using a Human judge [58].

4.2 Model Observation

Model Observation metrics require access to model outputs or internal activations but do not intervene on the model or its inputs. They occupy a middle ground in the access hierarchy, more informative than purely text-based comparison but less demanding than input perturbation. Figure 2 shows this family has reasonable coverage of Plausibility and Utility, but many metrics require access to Intrinsic properties of models, matching the family definition.

4.2.1 Output Contrastivity

Output Contrastivity metrics assess whether an explanation is discriminative with respect to the model’s output class [6]. This is only appropriate for CoT reasoning that is being applied to a classification task, and cannot be applied to more open-ended reasoning tasks. Confidence Indication [117] measures the similarity between the aggregate sentence token probabilities and the probability of the predicted class label. An explanation correlating with model confidence, or being sufficient to discriminate between classes, is considered a property of Utility [117]. Target Discriminativness [26] measures this by training an external model to recover the predicted class label from the explanation alone. Low discriminativness suggests the explanation is generic rather than specific to the model’s actual prediction, which conveys a lack of Plausibility.

4.2.2 Mutual Coherence

Mutual Coherence metrics assess the consistency between a model’s explanation and another explanation method applied to the same model, treating the second method as a proxy ground truth for what the model is actually attending to [6]. In the VXAI framework this group typically involves comparison across multiple XAI methods, but for CoT reasoning the relevant comparison is between the textual explanation and feature attribution values computed from the model’s internal activations. Comparison to Mechanistic Interpretability methods are separately grouped under Section 4.4 Model Intervention, as MI methods require direct access to model weights, whereas feature attribution methods only require access to model outputs. CC-SHAP [9] argues that input tokens contributing to the model’s answer prediction should contribute similarly to its explanation. It computes SHAP values for both prediction and explanation separately and compares them using an overlap-similarity score. SHAP Faithfulness [109] takes a related approach, comparing features extracted from the text explanation directly to SHAP values based on feature rank, sign and value agreement. A limitation of this group is treating feature attribution as a ground truth for faithfulness when they may just be plausible explanations unrelated to the model’s true internal computation [8]. These metrics are therefore better understood as measures of self-consistency between XAI methods, which can increase confidence and reliability in them, but does not directly measure faithfulness.

4.2.3 Significance Check

Significance check metrics test whether an explanation contains meaningfully more information than a random or uninformative baseline [6], using intrinsic model signals to quantify information content. This group addresses a common concern with CoT reasoning; an explanation can be coherent and consistent with an answer whilst contributing no genuine reasoning signal beyond generic text.

Perplexity-based metrics [68, 109] assess reasoning traces using token probability distributions. ROSCOE introduces two variants: perplexity-chain which scores a token using all previous tokens in current and prior steps, and perplexity-step which restricts context to the current step only [73]. Lower perplexity indicates the explanation closely follows common patterns in the model’s training distribution, which may signal a generic or templated response. However perplexity does not measure relevance to the specific input, a highly domain-specific explanation would score high perplexity for being out-of-distribution with respect to the models training data, but may still be irrelevant to the input. Rational Evaluation with V-information (REV) [118] and Estimated Pointwise V-information (EPVI) [119] address this more directly by measuring the amount of new information expressed in the explanation compared to the input and output answer. V-information measures predictive utility rather than statistical likelihood, making it more robust to model calibration than entropy-based measures.

Causal concept faithfulness [120] measures the alignment between the causal effects of input concepts and the rate at which they are mentioned in the explanation. It relies on an LLM to identify causal concepts, generate counterfactuals and judge the explanation attributes importance, and then uses KL divergence to measure the distance between the LLM derived and explanation-implied causal effect distributions. Similarly Shifting Attention to Relevance (SAR) [121] jointly examines token and sentence relevance to estimate uncertainty and detect hallucinations without a ground truth reference. It sits at the boundary of a significance check and a Factuality metric, and is useful in settings where no reference is available but a signal about explanation reliability is required.

4.2.4 Setup Consistency

Setup Consistency metrics assess whether the model produces stable explanations when the same input is presented multiple times, determining the consistency across repeated evaluations. SELFCKECHKGPT [122] is based on the assumption that if a model has genuine knowledge of a concept it will be consistent across sampled responses, whereas hallucinated content will diverge. It measures consistency between multiple responses to the same prompt using BERTScore, n-gram overlap and NLI entailment. Like SAR above it also provides a reference-free signal for Factuality.

4.3 Input Intervention

Input Intervention metrics perturb the model’s input and observe the resulting change in predictions or explanations, requiring repeated model inference but no access to model weights. This family has the strongest coverage of Continuity and Fidelity as shown in Figure 2, making it the most useful for probing beyond surface explanation quality. However many metrics in this family heavily rely on predictive performance evaluators, which require CoT reasoning to be applied to task-specific settings where ground truth labels exist.

4.3.1 Neighborhood Continuity

Neighborhood continuity metrics are based on the assumption that similar inputs should lead to similar explanations [6]. However this is challenging for CoT reasoning where multiple distinct but equally valid reasoning traces may exist for the same input, meaning high explanation variability does not necessarily indicate poor quality. Nevertheless, it is a popular technique for measuring Fidelity as it can be applied to closed-source LLMs and computed with only predictive performance and similarity evaluators.

Paraphrasing metrics measure robustness to minor lexical variations [36], whereas Data Consistency [117] compares inputs with and without masked random words and Synthetic neighbors [123] generates synthetic inputs in the neighborhood of the original instance. Robustness equivalence [124] adds Gaussian noise to input embeddings and measures if the changes in the predicted label and explanation are similarly robust. Finally, the Explain-Query-Test metric [125] prompts an LLM to generate multiple-choice questions from the explanation, paraphrases them, and measures model accuracy on these self-generated questions.

More structured approaches test specific aspects of the explanation robustness. The Input Reconstruction Test [126] tests if a model’s prediction on a reconstructed input differs from its prediction on the original. Inconsistency detection [68] similarly generates new inputs designed to cause contradictory explanations. These both require a benchmark with explanations that follows structures enabling reconstruction and contradiction – for example e-SNLI [68]. However this is expensive and inapplicable to explanations with greater variance in composition. PromptRobust [127] measures the performance drop rate following adversarial prompt attacks, providing a task-agnostic measure of explanation robustness to prompt manipulation.

4.3.2 Adversarial Input Resilience

Adversarial Input Resilience metrics apply targeted perturbations designed to test if an explanation changes appropriately when the input is modified in a way that should affect the model’s reasoning. If a perturbation changes the prediction but not the explanation, or prediction remains fixed but two very different explanations are produced, this can be a sign that faithfulness is compromised. However, this evidence remains indirect, since input-output consistency is a necessary but not sufficient condition for faithful reasoning [9]. A perturbed input leading to equal changes in a model’s prediction and explanation could be considered a measure of self-consistency instead, as faithfulness requires assessing the models internals directly [9]. Despite this, all metrics in this section claim to measure Fidelity through input perturbation and a performance or similarity score.

Corrupting CoT, such as Early Answering and Filler Tokens [4], and Adding Mistakes [36] insert errors into the reasoning steps and measure the resulting drop in task performance. A small performance drop when CoT is corrupted suggests the model was not genuinely using its stated reasoning. Similarly Biasing Features [2] appends a suggested answer to the prompt to lure the model towards a stereotyped and incorrect response, then measures the decrease in accuracy and evaluates whether the explanation acknowledges the bias using Human Judges. F-AUCROC [128] frames faithfulness as two binary classification problems, did the intervention change the prediction, and did the explanation include the inserted feature. Inter-explanation sufficiency [117] takes token probabilities of the explanation sentences, samples subsets, and measures whether selected and unselected subsets are sufficient as explanations to independently generate the same prediction.

Counterfactual reasoning assesses if an explanation changes when the original question is modified in a different direction, measured as the percentage of flipped predictions[36]. This is also used in the Counterfactual Test (CT) [126], which inserts tokens into the input that cause the model to give a different prediction, then check if these tokens also appear in the explanation. The Correlation Counterfactual Test (CCT) [129] builds upon CT, but instead of just measuring a change in model prediction it measures the change in model probability distributions over discrete output classes, and compares this to the probability that the added token appears in the explanation. Phi-CCT [128] is a drop-in replacement that removes the requirement for token probabilities, making it less susceptible to gaming.

However, explanations that do not include specific perturbed input tokens maybe simply be incomplete or limited by tight token limits, rather than unfaithful [130]. Rather than relying on the explanation explicitly repeating the intervention, Causal Mediation [130, 131] can be used to quantify how much of the prediction change after an input intervention is caused by the CoT reasoning compared to the intervention itself. The direct effect measures how the input intervention directly changes the model prediction, and the indirect effect measures how the CoT reasoning changes the model prediction whilst keeping the input fixed [132]. The changes in model prediction are calculated using model accuracy [131], or the change probability distribution (for multiple-choice) or output token probabilities (for free-text answers)[130]. Finally Causal Abstraction [133] relies on human-generated causal models, and matches intermediate nodes in the causal model to the corresponding variables in the CoT. It then tests whether the same intervention (change of token) applied to both the causal node and the corresponding CoT variable produced the same output. Results suggest CoT tokens do exhibit significant causal influence on final answers, though the strength varies substantially across tasks [133].

4.4 Model Intervention

Model intervention metrics alter the model itself to asses whether explanations depend meaningfully on the model’s internal state [6]. This family requires the deepest level of model access and is largely inaccessible for proprietary LLMs, and some techniques such as retraining or data randomization [6] are inaccessible even for open-source LLMs, as larger models are very computationally expensive to train and their full training data is not known. We have only included metrics that are relevant to CoT reasoning, and subsequently, as Figure 2 shows, the number of metrics in this family is much lower than others. This represents the frontier of CoT faithfulness evaluation, technically the most meaningful but practically the least accessible.

4.4.1 Internal Signal Metrics

Internal Signal metrics evaluate CoT reasoning by comparing them against signals derived directly from the model’s internal representations, like activations, gradients and sparse autoencoder features. Unlike all other metric groups, which treat the model as a black box and infer interpretability from input-output behavior, these metrics open the model and examine its computation directly. This makes them the closest available approximation to ground truth for Fidelity evaluation, whilst introducing the assumption that the methods for representing model internals are themselves faithful to the true model’s internal decision making.

Feature importance agreement [124] uses gradient-based attribution to identify tokens important for label prediction and tests whether these align with tokens important for rationale generation. Faithfulness by unlearning reasoning steps (FUR) [134] deletes information contained in the reasoning steps from the model parameters and measures the change in the model’s prediction, reporting both difference in final model label and change in probability distribution for each reasoning step. Causal Faithfulness [135] measures the divergence between a causal matrix derived from activation patching over model layers and the CoT explanation, using cosine distance as the divergence metric. Activation patching, substituting activations from one forward pass into another, provides causal evidence of which internal pathways are functionally necessary for the prediction, which can then be compared against what the explanation claims drove the reasoning. Rank-One Model Editing (ROME) [136] builds on Causal Mediation Analysis from Section 4.3 but rather than using input interventions, it changes neural activations that correspond to factual association to see if the model faithfully updates its reasoning. Simulated Neurons [137] evaluates the quality of CoT reasoning of individual neurons by testing whether an explanation is sufficient to reproduce that neuron’s behavior. GPT-4 generates candidate explanations from the top-activating token contexts for each neuron, then simulates the neuron’s activations based solely on those explanations. Explanation quality is scored as the correlation between the simulated and real activation values, a high correlation indicates the explanation captures what the neuron is actually responding to. ReasonScore [138] measures the contribution of individual sparse autoencoder features to vocabulary associated with reasoning or thinking, for example ‘maybe’, ‘but’ and ‘wait’. This identifies whether specific internal features associated with reasoning behavior are active, representing the extent to which the model is engaging in reasoning, rather than the quality of the reasoning produced.

There are three main limitations within this group. First, attribution and probing methods identify correlations between activations and features but do not establish causal necessity, and this can be further confused by redundant circuits in large models [94]. Second, large LLMs often use multiple parallel pathways simultaneously when generating CoT. This means that a single faithful mechanism for any reasoning step may not exist [94]. Third, all methods require open-source models with accessible weights, excluding the proprietary systems where CoT interpretability evaluation is most practically needed. These constraints do not diminish the value of internal signal metrics but do substantially limit their applicability for practitioners.

4.5 A Priori Constrained

A Prior Constrained metrics require specific architectural choices, training setups or experimental conditions to be established before evaluation begins. As noted in Section 3.3, this family in the original VXAI framework [6] also includes metrics requiring ground-truth datasets, which we have re-classified into Explanans-Centric on the basis that data availability is an evaluator decision rather than a model access constraint. In practice, this family is inapplicable to CoT reasoning evaluation for a fundamental reason: no human fully understands the internal computations of these models well enough to design an experiment that directly verifies whether an explanation is faithful to them [29, 13]. There is also no interpretable surrogate model that can replicate the reasoning capabilities of a large LLM. The A Priori constraint cannot be satisfied. This is not a gap in the literature so much as a reflection of the current limits of our understanding of LLM computation. There is a direct implication for this entire catalog: every interpretability metric identified is, at best, an indirect proxy for ground truth that cannot yet be established.

5 Analysis and Limitations

The metrics catalog reveals several structural patterns in how CoT interpretability is currently evaluated, and several equally important gaps in what is not being evaluated. This section synthesizes these findings into five observations, each with implications for how practitioners should select and interpret evaluation metrics.

5.1 Coverage Gaps

Figure 2 makes the coverage asymmetry of the current metric landscape immediately visible. Fidelity and Plausibility account for the overwhelming majority of identified metrics, whilst Parsimony, Coverage and Efficiency have almost no dedicated metrics. Efficiency in particular, the requirement that explanations be computable broadly and at reasonable cost, has no dedicated metrics in the catalog. This likely reflects the fact that for CoT reasoning, explanation generation cost is dwarfed by the cost of the evaluators themselves – running mechanistic interpretability methods or collecting human judgments is orders of magnitude more expensive than generating a reasoning trace. Efficiency is therefore a property of the evaluation pipeline rather than the explanation, and is implicitly addressed by the evaluator ordering in Section 3.2.

The coverage of Continuity is concentrated almost entirely in the Input Intervention family, thus it is difficult to measure without the ability to perturb inputs and run repeated inference. For practitioners working with closed-source models via API this is accessible, but adds non-trivial computation cost. Consistency is better distributed but still thin, as alternatives to input intervention involve measuring consistency compared to another XAI technique such as SHAP or gradient-based attribution, which also add computational cost.

Utility has reasonable coverage in the Explanans-Centric family though Simulatability and inter-reasoning metrics such as Information Gain and Correctness, and some further coverage in Model Observation through information-theory approaches including REV and EPVO. However, coverage drops sharply at deeper access levels, and the Simulatability metrics that provide the most direct measurement of Utility rely heavily on human or LLM judges as their evaluator.

5.2 Faithfulness or Self-Consistency?

Measuring faithfulness to a model’s true internal computation relies on the assumption that it is possible to have a ground truth for how these model’s work, despite them being entirely black-box. Therefore most metrics in this catalog cannot directly measure faithfulness, and are, at best, indirect proxies. This has previously been highlighted through the claim that existing faithfulness metrics can only measure the self-consistency between model and explanation [9], specifically for metrics that rely on consistency with other interpretability methods which may themselves be unfaithful.

Metrics reliant on Human Judgment could also be considered self-consistent rather than faithful, reflecting the fundamental limit established in Section 4.5: no human fully understands the internal computations of large LLMs well enough to construct a ground truth against which faithfulness can be verified. Some would argue Human Judgment only measure Plausibility or Utility, as these desiderata are grounded in human evaluation and don’t require understanding the model’s causal reasoning process [8, 9].

The Input Intervention family provides the largest number of Fidelity metrics, as if corrupting the reasoning changes the prediction or if inserting a biasing feature changes the explanation, this constitutes causal evidence about the role of reasoning in the model’s behavior [2, 4]. However, many of these metrics measure input-output consistency, ruling out specific scenarios the explanation could be unfaithful to its prediction, rather than genuine causal effect [124].

5.3 Benchmark Limitations

Many metrics rely on comparison to ground truth data benchmarks, as described in Section 4.1.2. A compounding problem when relying on ground truth is data contamination. Most established benchmarks are likely to have appeared in the pretraining data of recent LLMs, meaning that performance scores may reflect memorization rather than reasoning [77]. This is particularly consequential for CoT evaluation, where a model can produce a plausible, coherent reasoning trace by retrieving a memorized solution rather than reasoning through the problem, and most metrics cannot distinguish these cases [77]. Strategies to mitigate contamination include private or dynamic benchmarks, data regeneration and filtering, and benchmark-free evaluation using LLM and Human judges [77]. None of these are fully satisfactory, as contamination remains an open challenge for any evaluation that relies on fixed benchmark datasets.

A related concern is Goodhart’s Law applied to explanation benchmarks. It has been demonstrated that the ERASER comprehensiveness and sufficiency metrics, two of the most widely used faithfulness proxies, can be inflated dramatically without altering predictions or explanations, by exploiting the out-of-distribution nature of masked inputs [139]. Once a metric is optimized for, it ceases to be a reliable indicator of the underlying property. This is particularly concerning for CoT evaluation where the metrics are already indirect proxies – optimizing a model’s CoT to score well on plausibility metrics may actually degrade interpretability without any metric detecting the change.

5.4 Evaluator Reliability

The reliability of evaluators used to compute interpretability metrics is itself a significant concern, and meta-evaluations that assess how well metrics correlate with human judgment reveal systematic weaknesses across all evaluator types.

Overlap-based similarity metrics, the second most common evaluator type in the catalog, show consistently low correlation with human judgments on explanation quality [25, 81]. ROUGE and BERTScore correlate less with human judgment than entailment-based metrics in large-scale summarization evaluation studies [81], and this finding is likely to be even stronger for CoT reasoning where valid explanations can differ substantially in surface form.

LLM-as-a-judge introduces its own reliability concerns, having shown consistently underwhelming results in correlation with human judgment [97, 140]. Judge accuracy is also highly sensitive to prompt wording, varying significantly even with semantically equivalent evaluation prompts [97, 98]. Position bias, verbosity bias and self enhancement bias, where the judge favors outputs from its own model family, are also well-documented failure modes [97]. Sycophancy

compounds this further, as instruction-tuned LLMs systematically adjust their assessments to follow user-implied preferences even when those preferences conflict with correct evaluation [141].

Given the desire for more causality-based metrics [130], it is particularly concerning that LLMs perform relatively poorly in causal reasoning [48, 142], and have demonstrated causal hallucination and sensitivity to words expressing causal concepts in prompts [48].

Human Evaluation, despite being the gold standard, faces its own reliability limitations. The most pervasive concern in the catalog is sample size, many metrics based on Ground Truth Benchmarks conduct human evaluations on fewer than 100 examples and use these to validate automated metrics [106, 102, 105, 107, 103, 72, 86, 108], which limits the statistical power of any conclusions drawn. Whether human judgment is even the appropriate gold standard for CoT reasoning tasks, when humans are unable to truly assess interpretability from the explanation text alone, remains an open question. It is more accurate to instead measure a humans perception of a system, for example human trust in a system can be measured through survey or interview [61, 95, 59, 54]. However, it has been shown that any explanation, even placebic ones, still lead to greater trust than no explanation at all [56], demonstrating that human perception of a system does not measure how the system is actually working in practice.

5.5 The Access Gap

The metric families defined in Section 3.3 reveal a structural mismatch between the models where CoT interpretability evaluation is most needed and the models where it is most feasible. As Figure 2 shows, the majority of metrics with meaningful Fidelity coverage require Input Intervention access or above. Model Intervention metrics, including the Internal Signal group that provides the most direct evidence for faithfulness, require open-source models with accessible weights.

The large proprietary LLMs that dominate deployed CoT reasoning, namely GPT-4, Claude and Gemini, are accessible only via API, restricting practitioners to the Explanans-Centric, Model Observation and Input Intervention families. Input Intervention requires only repeated inference calls, which APIs support, albeit at a greater computational cost. Within these three families, practitioners have access to meaningful Fidelity coverage through adversarial input resilience metrics as well as strong coverage of Plausibility, Factuality and Consistency. The hard boundary is when practitioners want to measure beyond input-output consistency as a faithfulness proxy, as this boundary is insurmountable for closed-sourced models.

The access gap also affects the model intervention metrics such as data and hyperparameter randomization sanity checks that serve as a principled baseline in other XAI evaluation contexts [6]. As noted in Section 4.4, neither can be applied to pretrained LLMs where training data and architecture are unknown. The evaluation infrastructure that XAI research has developed for simpler models does not transfer to the setting where it is most urgently needed.

Mitigation strategies are limited but not absent. Reference-free intrinsic interpretability metrics and LLM-as-a-judge can partially compensate for the lack of deeper access. Mechanistic interpretability research on open-source models can inform understanding of proprietary model behavior, with appropriate caveats about transferability. And the growing availability of open-weight frontier models, such as Llama, Mistral, Qwen, and Deepseek, provides an expanding set of models where the full metric catalog is applicable. However, for the proprietary models, the access gap remains structurally unresolved, and practitioners should design their evaluation strategies with explicit acknowledgment of what cannot be measured given the access they have.

6 Challenges and Future Work

6.1 Metric Bundles

A practical response to some limitations is to evaluate CoT reasoning using metric bundles, carefully selected combinations of metrics targeting different desiderata and evaluator types, rather than relying on a single metric.

Combining metrics has several statistical advantages, as agreement across independent metrics provides stronger evidence than a second score, and metrics targeting different desiderata serve as mutual checks. Combining correlational metrics with at least one intervention based metric, where access allows, provides a partial causal anchor for the metric bundle, reducing the reliance on correlation alone whilst also minimizing API inference costs where possible.

Figure 3 shows some example metric bundles for different deployment scenarios, with different target desiderata (target icon) and model access (key icon). These are illustrative, the appropriate selection of metrics will depend on the task, available data and resource constraints.

Figure 3: Example metric bundles for three deployment scenarios, illustrating how target desiderata (target icon), model access level (key icon) and evaluator mix jointly constrain metric selection. Bundles are illustrative rather than prescriptive, the appropriate selection of metrics will depend on task structure, available data and resource constraints.

The practitioner workflow introduced in Section 3 can be used to construct an effective metric bundle, by selecting metrics that together cover the desiderata relevant to the application, span multiple evaluator types and are feasible given the available model access. Appendix 8.2, Tables 3 and 4 are designed to support bundle construction by making the desiderata coverage and evaluator composition of each metric explicit, enabling practitioners to identify complementary metrics that collectively address the properties they care about.

6.2 Evaluations Beyond Verifiable Tasks

A substantial portion of the metrics catalog quantifies interpretability using predictive performance on a downstream task. This is only applicable to verifiable tasks, those where a ground truth benchmark exists and answers can be evaluated as correct or incorrect.

Recently there has been a focus on removing the need for curating ground truth labels, with benchmarks such as MiniF2F [75] and systems such as AlphaProof [76] demonstrating that within formal mathematical domains, proof correctness can be mechanically verified, dissolving the need for ground truth labels. Within verifiable domains, these are great methodological advances. However, the domains where CoT interpretability matters most, such as in clinical decision support, financial analysis, policy forecasting, and open-ended scientific reasoning, are precisely the domains where formal verification is impossible and ground truth answers do not exist.

This need for a model to perform a downstream task in order to measure interpretability appears as a coverage gap in our analysis; an absence of automated, reference-free metrics, especially for Factualty and Utility desiderata. A principled evaluation framework for open-ended reasoning, one that does not depend on task correctness as a proxy for explanation quality, remains largely undeveloped. Progress here likely requires drawing on methods from social science and cognitive psychology like [54] to assess explanation quality in terms of user understanding and decision support rather than answer correctness, and developing scalable approximations of these human-centered assessments that can be applied without per-task human annotation.

6.3 Causally Grounded Evaluation

To combat the limitation of only measuring self-consistency, a small number of metrics try and establish whether the CoT causally influences the model’s prediction. A genuine causal effect of the CoT on the output implies that this relationship is implemented in the model’s internal computation - the causal link must exist somewhere in the model’s mechanism.

The metric with the strongest causal grounding is Causal Faithfulness [135], which uses activation patching to directly establish which internal pathways are causally necessary for the prediction. Feature Importance Agreement [124] constitutes a genuine causal test albeit on a retrained model rather than the original. Causal Abstraction [133] offers a structured intervention but ultimately relies on a human-derived causal graph to define what the causal structure should be, meaning if the graph is incorrect the causal claims it produces are invalid. It is therefore better understood as testing consistency with a human causal model. Causal Diagnosticity [143] is a meta-evaluation framework which generates unfaithful explanations through editing the model’s internal knowledge, and uses these to evaluate CoT interpretability metrics, with Filler Tokens [4] performing better than CC-SHAP [9] and Counterfactual Simulatability [116].

These metrics provide indirect but principled evidence about the internal workings, however the ones with the strongest causal grounding require full access to model weights, meaning they are inaccessible for proprietary models, the models where faithfulness evaluation is most urgently needed.

Developing causal evaluation methods that operate via API alone is therefore a critical research direction. Causal Mediation Analysis [130, 131] represents a promising direction, as it uses token probabilities rather than internal activations to quantify causal influence. Yet, token probabilities have been shown to reflect model calibration rather than genuine causal mechanisms [91, 92], and further work is needed to establish when probability-based causal estimates are reliable. Carefully designed natural experiments, where inputs are systematically varied to isolate causal effects, offer another avenue that does not require weight access, but require methodological development specific to the CoT setting.

7 Conclusion

Chain-of-thought reasoning has become the dominant mode of explanation for large language models, yet the field lacks systematic understanding of how to evaluate whether these explanations are genuinely related to the model’s inner working. This survey addresses that gap by providing a practical framework for navigating the CoT interpretability metric landscape, structured around three axes that reflect the real constraints practitioners face, namely: what properties they want to measure, what evaluators are available given their data and resources, and what level of model access they have.

Across the catalog of metrics identified, several findings stand out. Fidelity and Plausibility are heavily covered whilst Continuity and Consistency remain largely unmeasured, particularly at the lower access levels. Most existing metrics are an indirect proxy for faithfulness, and many metrics routinely described as measuring Fidelity are in practice measuring Plausibility. The metrics that provide the strongest evidence for faithfulness through causally-grounded approaches require access to model weights, meaning they cannot be used on proprietary LLMs.

The three-axis framework and Appendix 8.2, Tables 3 and 4 are designed to make these distinctions actionable. A practitioner can identify which desiderata are relevant to their application, where evaluators are feasible given their resources, and which metric families can be used given their model access, then use the tables to identify the metrics that sit at the intersection of these constraints. We recommend composing metric bundles rather than relying on any single metric, combining correlational and intervention-based measures where possible, and being explicit about what each metric in the bundle can and cannot establish.

In the near future, the most important open problems are the extension of causal evaluation methods to closed-source models, and the construction of principled evaluation frameworks for open-ended unverifiable tasks – the settings where CoT interpretability evaluation matters most and current methods are least adequate. Progress on these problems will require both methodological innovation and closer engagement between XAI, causal inference and human-computer interaction communities. This survey aims to provide the foundation from which that work can proceed.

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8 Appendices

8.1 Search Queries

8.1.1 Scopus

Query 1:

```
TITLE ("explainable" OR "XAI" OR "interpret*" OR "faithful*" OR
"rationalization") AND ("large language model*" OR "llm" OR
"natural language explanation*" OR "NLE" OR "reasoning" OR
"chain of thought" OR "cot") AND ("survey" OR "review")
```

Query 2:

```
TITLE("explainable" OR "XAI" OR "interpret*" OR "faithful*" OR
"rationalization") AND ("evaluating" OR "evaluate" OR "evaluation" )
AND ("survey" OR "review")
```

8.1.2 arXiv

Query 1

```
order: -announced_date_first; size: 50; include_cross_list: True;
terms: AND title="explainable" OR "XAI" OR "interpretability" OR
"faithful*" OR "rationalization"; AND title="large language model*" OR
"llm" OR "natural language explanation*" OR "NLE" OR "reasoning" OR
"chain of thought" OR "cot"; AND title="survey" OR "review"
```

Query 2

```
order: -announced_date_first; size: 50; include_cross_list: True;
terms: AND title="explainable" OR "XAI" OR "interpretability" OR
"faithful*" OR "rationalization"; AND title="evaluating" OR "evaluate"
OR "evaluation"; AND title="survey" OR "review"
```

8.2 Metric Catalog

	Metric Group	Metric Name	Pars.	Plaus.	Cov.	Fid.	Cont.	Cons.	Eff.	Fact.	Util.	
Explanans-Centric	Size[6]	Length		✓								
	Ground Truth	Benchmarks			✓	✓				✓		
	Factual Comparison		Q^2 [112]								✓	
			factENT[113]								✓	
			CEQ[74]								✓	✓
			Approximated Factuality[66]								✓	
			fact _{acc} [114]								✓	
			FACTSCORE[65],PK[115]							✓		
	Input Contrastivity[6]		Semantic Similarity[73]		✓		✓					
			Source-consistency[73].		✓		✓				✓	
Inter-reasoning		Semantic Alignment[73]		✓						✓	✓	
		Self-Consistency[73]		✓								
		Correctness[67]									✓	
		Information Gain[67]									✓	
Simulatability		LAS[36]									✓	
		Counterfactual Simulatability[116]									✓	
		acc_improvement[60]									✓	
		Human prediction[95]		✓							✓	
		Human mental model[61, 95]		✓							✓	
Input Coverage[6]		Hallucination & Safety Refusal[58]		✓	✓					✓		
Model Observation	Output Contrastivity[6]		Confidence Indication[117]		✓						✓	
			Target Discrimination[26]		✓							✓
	Mutual Coherence[6]		CC-SHAP[9]		✓		✓*		✓		✓	
			SHAP faithfulness[109]		✓		✓*		✓		✓	
	Significance Check[6]		Perplexity[68] [109]					✓				✓
Perplexity-chain[73]				✓							✓	
REV[118]											✓	
EPVI[119]											✓	
Causal Concept Faithfulness[120]				✓			✓				✓	
		SAR[121]							✓	✓		
Set-up Consistency[6]		SELFCKEKGPT[122]						✓		✓		
Input Intervention	Neighborhood Continuity[6]		Input Reconstruction[126]		✓		✓					
			Explain-Query-Test[125]					✓				
			Paraphrasing[36]					✓		✓		
			Diversity Consistency[117]					✓				
			Synthetic Neighbors[123]					✓				
			Inconsistent explanations[144]					✓		✓		
			Robustness Equiv.[124]					✓		✓		
	PromptRobust[127]					✓						
	Adversarial Input Resilience[6]		F-AUROC[128]				✓*					
			Biasing Features[2]				✓*	✓				
Inter-expl Sufficiency[117]						✓*				✓		
Corrupting CoT[4] [36]						✓*						
Counterfactual Reasoning[36]						✓						
Counterfactual Test[126]						✓						
CCT[129]						✓						
phi-CCT[128]						✓						
Causal Mediation[130, 131]						✓						
Causal abstraction[133]						✓						
Model Intervention	Internal Signal Metrics		Causal Faithfulness[135]		✓		✓					
			FUR[134]				✓					
			Feature Importance Agreement[124]		✓		✓		✓			
			RÖME[136]		✓		✓			✓	✓	
			Simulated Neurons[137]		✓		✓		✓			
			Reason Score[138]		✓		✓					

Table 3: Evaluation metrics compared to desired properties. Metric families and groupings derived from [6]. *It has been argued that these metrics measure self-consistency rather than Fidelity.

	Metric Group	Metric Name	Perf	Overlap Sim	Model Sim	Intr Interp	Mech Interp	LLM	Human	
Explanans-Centric	Size[6]	Length				✓				
	Ground Truth	Benchmarks	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	
	Factual Comparison		Q^2 [112]			✓				
			factENT[113]		✓	✓				
			CEQ[74]			✓				
			Approximated Factuality[66]		✓					
			fact _{acc} [114]				✓			
FACTSCORE[65], PK[115]							✓	✓		
Input Contrastivity[6]	Semantic Similarity[73] Source-consistency[73].			✓						
Inter-reasoning		Semantic Alignment[73]		✓	✓	✓				
		Self-Consistency[73]			✓					
		Correctness[67]			✓	✓				
		Information Gain[67]	✓			✓				
Simulatability		LAS[36]	✓							
		Counterfactual Simulatability[116]		✓	✓			✓	✓	
		acc_improvement[60]						✓		
		Human perception[95]							✓	
		Human mental model[61, 95]							✓	
Input Coverage[6]	Hallucination & Safety Refusal[58]	✓			✓			✓		
Model Observation	Output Contrastivity[6]	Confidence Indication[117]	✓	✓		✓				
		Target Discriminativeness[26]	✓							
	Mutual Coherence[6]	CC-SHAP[9] SHAP faithfulness[109]		✓	✓					
					✓					
	Significance Check[6]		Perplexity[68] [109]		✓		✓			
Perplexity-chain[73]						✓				
REV[118]						✓				
EPVI[119]						✓				
Causal Concept Faithfulness[120]			✓	✓				✓		
SAR[121]	✓			✓						
Set-up Consistency[6]	SELFCKEKGPT[122]		✓	✓			✓			
Input Intervention	Neighborhood Continuity[6]	Input Reconstruction Test[126]	✓	✓						
		Explain-Query-Test[125]	✓							
		Paraphrasing[36]	✓							
		Data Consistency[117]		✓						
		Synthetic Neighbors[123]		✓	✓					
		Inconsistent Explanations[144]				✓				
		Robustness Equivalence[124]	✓			✓				
		PromptRobust[127]	✓							
	Adversarial Input Resilience[6]		F-AUROC[128]	✓	✓					
			Biasing Features[2]	✓						✓
			Inter-expl sufficiency[117]	✓			✓			
			Corrupting CoT[4] [36]	✓						
			Counterfactual Reasoning[36]		✓					
			Counterfactual Test[126]	✓	✓					
			CCT[129]	✓	✓		✓			
phi-CCT[128]	✓	✓								
Causal Mediation[130, 131]	✓			✓						
Causal abstraction[133]								✓		
Model Intervention	Internal Signal Metrics	Causal Faithfulness[135]					✓			
		FUR[134]				✓	✓			
		Feature Importance Agreement[124]	✓	✓			✓			
		ROME[136]	✓				✓			
		Simulated Neurons[137]				✓	✓			
		Reason Score[138]				✓	✓			

Table 4: Evaluation metrics compared to evaluator computation implementations. Metric families and groupings derived from [6]

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